

ISic1649

Funerary inscription for Zosime

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

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Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 531

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 23.4 cm

Width 31.6 cm

Depth 3.2-3.8 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 14-29 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. Sanctissimae
2. coniug i coniugi Zosime
3. [fi]del[i], q ue quae bixsit vixit
4. ann (is) XXVI et de
5. ce[s]sit XI Kal (endas) Octobris
6. Amantio
7. et Albino cons (ulibus)

Apparatus

Translation (en)

For my most holy wife, Zosime, strong in faith, who lived for 26 years and departed 11 days before

the Kalends of October, in the consulship of Amantius and Albinus (= 21 September 345 AD)

Translation (it)

Per la mia santissima moglie, Zosime, forte nella fede, che ha vissuto per 26 anni e se ne andò 11

giorni prima delle calende di ottobre, sotto il consolato di Amantius e Albino (21 settembre 345 d.C.).

Commentary

This is one of relatively few Christian epitaphs in Latin from Catania. The name Zosime is a common Greek one, found several times in eastern Sicily. Giving a date by referring to the consuls in office during that year reflects standard Roman dating practice, but giving the precise date of death in a funerary inscription is a distinctive feature of Christian funerary epigraphy, and this is one of the earliest Sicilian examples to use a consular date. The misspelling of vixit as bixsit reflects a common confusion of 'B' and 'V' (due to a merging of the sound represented by each letter in Latin). This is more common in southern than northern Italy, and in this case may well represent the influence of Greek (where use of β for a Latin V is commonplace; see no.24).

Digital identifiers:

TM 175849

EDR 073195

EDCS 16100302

Bibliography

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